

(A.R.) was added. The solution was evaporated to dryness, diluted with 10 ml distilled water and again evaporated to dryness. After diluting it with 150 ml distilled water, any adherent of nitric acid was just neutralised by 1:1 ammonia solution. The 1%(w/v) reagent solution was then added, the yellowish green precipitate was determined as described earlier. The results of estimation of Pd(II) and Ni(II) are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SEPARATION AND DETERMINATION OF Pd(II) AND Ni(II) IN THEIR BINARY MIXTURE

Metal ion taken (mg)		Complex obtained (mg)		Metal ion found (mg)		% Error	
Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)
12.00	11.72	48.6	78.8	12.00	11.76	0.00	+0.34
12.00	23.44	48.8	153.6	12.04	23.53	+0.33	+0.36
24.00	11.72	97.4	76.4	24.04	11.70	+0.16	-0.17
24.00	23.44	97.2	153.4	23.79	23.50	-0.04	+0.25
30.00	15.62	121.6	101.8	30.02	15.59	+0.06	-0.19
30.00	31.24	121.4	203.4	29.97	31.16	-0.10	-0.25

Acknowledgement

We wish to record our sincere thanks to Dr. R. N. Gupta, Principal and Dr. B. C. Banerjee (Reader), Hindu College, Moradabad, for providing all necessary facilities.

References

1. N. SINGH, R. KUMAR and R. C. AGARWAL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1977, **46**, 851.
2. N. SINGH, R. KUMAR and B. D. KANSAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 1005.
3. N. SINGH, R. KUMAR, R. C. AGARWAL, and V. K. MAHESHWARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 961.

Thiophene-2-Aldoxime as a Gravimetric Reagent for Rhodium(III)*

HEMANT GUPTA and D. N. PATKAR

Department of Chemistry, University of Bombay, Vidyanagari, Bombay-400 098

Manuscript received 20 May 1978, revised 28 February 1979, accepted 6 June 1979

It has been found during investigation of analytical applications of thiophene-2-aldoxime in this laboratory that this reagent reacts with Rh(III) in neutral and alkaline medium to form a yellow-coloured complex which is insoluble in water and ethanol. A rapid gravimetric method for determination of rhodium based on this reaction is described.

* The paper was presented at the Convention of Chemists, Jaipur, 25-29th Dec., 1977.

Experimental

An expanded scale pH meter supplied by the Electronics Corporation of India, Ltd., Hyderabad, was employed for pH measurements. Rh(III) solutions were prepared from $\text{RhCl}_3 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Johnson Matthey, London) and standardised¹ by reduction to Rh. Thiophene-2-aldehyde was prepared by the method described by Weston and Michaels². It was converted into its oxime by the usual method. The oxime, m. p. 132-34°, was used for the analytical work in the form of a 1% ethanolic solution.

Analysis of the yellow precipitate formed by Rh(III) with thiophene-2-aldoxime (found: Rh, 21.0%; C, 37.52%; H, 2.67%; N, 8.05%; S, 20.20%; required for $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{ONS})_3$: Rh, 21.4%; C, 37.42%; H, 2.50%; N, 8.73%; S, 19.96%) suggests it to be a tris-complex. It is stable to heat up to 120°.

Results and Discussion

Analytical results indicate that the precipitation of Rh(III) is quantitative in the pH range 10.5-11.0. It was also found that a 50% excess of the reagent over the calculated amount is required. The excess reagent can be easily removed by washing with hot water or 5% ethanol. The washed precipitate was dried at 110° and weighed. Table 1 shows the results

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF RHODIUM AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

Rh(III) taken (mg)	Rh(III) found (mg)	% Error
4.56	4.25	6.80
9.11	9.08	0.33
13.67	13.61	0.44
18.22	18.23	0.05
22.78	22.68	0.44
27.33	27.31	0.07
31.89	31.67	0.67

of estimation of rhodium with the reagent at different amounts of the metal. It may be seen that rhodium, in amounts 10-30 mg can be determined gravimetrically with thiophene-2-aldoxime with a maximum error of 0.44%. Reproducibility studies carried out on five samples each containing 18.22 mg of Rh(III) gave an average error of 0.04 mg and a maximum error of 0.66%. The standard deviation was 0.0029.

Procedure for Determination of Rhodium:

Dilute the sample solution containing 10-30 mg of Rh(III) to about 100-125 ml with water. To this add 25 ml of a 1% ethanolic solution of thiophene-2-aldoxime with stirring. Adjust the pH to 10.5-11.0 with dilute NaOH. Digest the precipitate on a water bath for about 30 min. Allow to cool and filter through a preweighed sintered glass crucible

(porosity G_4). Wash the precipitate with hot water and finally with 5% ethanol to remove the excess of reagent. Dry at 110° to a constant weight and weigh as $\text{Rh}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{ONS})_3$. The factor for Rh is 0.2140.

Thiophene-2-aldoxime has been reported⁸ to precipitate palladium(II) quantitatively at pH 0.2-0.8. It has also been found in this laboratory that osmium(VIII) is precipitated by this reagent at a pH < 2. Further, platinum(II) is not precipitated by the reagent. Separation of Rh(III) from Pt, Pd and Os was therefore studied. From a mixture containing Pd(II) and Rh(III), palladium was precipitated by the reagent at pH 0.2-0.8. The precipitate, after digestion, was filtered and washed with hot water. The filtrate and the washings containing Rh(III) were collected carefully and concentrated to about 100 ml. Rh(III) was then precipitated by addition of more reagent and raising the pH to 10.5-11.0. Estimation of rhodium was completed as described above. Pd(II) precipitate was weighed as $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{ONS})_2\text{Cl}_2$ after drying at 110° . Results are given in Table 2. Similarly, Rh(III) was

References

1. F. J. NEWTON, "Textbook of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. IX, Charles Griffin & Co. Ltd., 1922, p. 334.
2. A. W. WESTON and R. J. MICHAELS, in "Organic Syntheses" Coll. Vol. 4, John Wiley, 1963, p. 915.
3. S. G. TANDON and S. C. BHATTACHARYA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 32, 194.

Studies of Complex Formation between 2-Hydroxy-5-Chloroacetophenone Oxime and Oxotitanium(IV)—Gravimetric Determination of Titanium

NEPAL SINGH*, B. D. KANSAL, A. C. OJHA**

and

HAMBIR SINGH***

Department of Chemistry, Hindu College, Moradabad

Manuscript received 22 September 1978, revised 23 March 1979, accepted 6 June 1979

AMONG few reagents employed for the estimation of titanium as its complex are 8-hydroxy quinoline^{1,2}, 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxy quinoline^{3,4} and *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime^{6,7}. The main utility of this reagent over the well known methods is that the titanium chelate can be precipitated in a wide pH range and weighed directly after drying at 120-130°. The substitution of chlorine in the parent *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime increases the sensitivity and accuracy. The interference due to several ions has been removed by controlling the pH or by using suitable masking agents.

The reagent 2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime form coloured precipitate with copper(II) (at pH 2.5-8.0), Ni(II) (pH 4.5-8.5), Co(II) (pH 5.0-9.0), Oxovanadium(IV) (pH 4.5-8.5). It has now been observed that titanium(IV) is quantitatively precipitated as a reddish yellow metal chelate $[\text{Ti}(\text{OH})\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{ClNO}_2]_2$ with this reagent in the pH range 3.5-8.5.

Materials and Methods

The reagent(HCAO) was prepared by Fries⁸ migration of *p*-chlorophenyl acetate in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. It was then converted into its oxime by refluxing it with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate. The product was recrystallised from ethanol(m.p. 185°). Reagent solution (0.5%) was prepared in 50% ethanol.

A weighed amount of potassium titanium oxalate(B. D. H.) was digested in conc. sulphuric

TABLE 2

(a) SEPARATION OF RHODIUM AND PLATINUM

Rh(III) taken = 9.11 mg

Pt(II) taken mg	Rh(III) found mg
10.32	9.07
10.32	9.04

(b) SEPARATION OF RHODIUM AND PALLADIUM

Rh(III) taken = 9.11 mg

Pd(II) taken mg	Rh(III) found mg	Pd(II) found mg
5.70	9.11	5.31
5.70	9.11	5.41
11.40	9.00	11.20
11.40	9.01	11.20

(c) SEPARATION OF RHODIUM AND OSMIUM

Rh(III) taken = 9.11 mg

Os(VIII) taken mg	Rh(III) found mg
5.00	9.11
5.00	9.00

separated from Os(VIII) by prior precipitation at pH 1.8-2.0 of osmium and estimation of rhodium in the filtrate as described above. The results are given in Table 2. The separations are rapid, clean and quantitative.

Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) which react with thiophene-2-aldoxime interfere in the estimation of rhodium.

* To whom all correspondence should be made.

** Chemistry Department, Sahu Jain College, Najibabad.

*** Chemistry Department, D. S. College, Aligarh.